

HI PHOTOPIC

PSAM 4238

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4239

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4088

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4066

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4155

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4156

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4188

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

HG PHOTOPIC

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4073

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4122

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4124

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 7899

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 7948

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 7970

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 8054

PSAM 8162

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 8188

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

LE PHOTOPIC

PSAM 4056

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4090

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4092

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4094

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4095

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4102

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4103

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4123

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4172

Left: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 3 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

HI SCOTOPIC

PSAM 4238

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4239

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4088

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4066

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4155

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4156

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4188

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

HG SCOTOPIC

PSAM 189

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4073

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4122

Left: 10 Cd.s.m⁻²

Right: 10 Cd.s.m⁻²

PSAM 4124

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 7899

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 7948

Left: 10 Cd.s.m⁻²

Right: 10 Cd.s.m⁻²

PSAM 7977

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 8054

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 8162

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 8188

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

LE SCOTOPIC

PSAM 4056

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4077

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4081

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2} Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4092

Left: 10 Cd.s.m⁻²

Right: 10 Cd.s.m⁻²

PSAM 4094

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4095

Left: 10 Cd.s.m⁻²

Right: 10 Cd.s.m⁻²

PSAM 4102

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4103

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4123

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

PSAM 4117

Left: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

Right: 10 Cd.s.m^{-2}

